

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF MEDICAL STUDENTS

Khujaakhmatova Qunduz Bakhtiyarovna

Tashkent Medical Academy, teacher

xojaaxmatovaqunduz@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551996>

Annotation

This article is dedicated to analyze effectiveness of innovative technologies in teaching FL to medical students and purpose to improve professional skills of students who are pursuing their career in medical disciplines. Also the article deals with theoretical and practical novelty of using innovative technologies in teaching medical terms and making students utilize them in professional area.

Key words: innovative technologies, strategies, method, techniques, medical English, learner-centered, professional skills, teacher's role, linguodidactic approach.

As modern technologies has enlarged and widely used in all fields the demand for using innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages whether it is based on ESP(English as a Specific Purpose) or EOP(English as an Occupational Purpose). It is remarkable to mention that nowadays, ESP is not more problematic issue rather than the past while acceptable authentic materials are provided. Prior to discussing about teaching methods and strategies of medical English it is vital to come up with the notion of ESP and its important features. Dudley Evans he mentions the following characteristics of ESP which concerns the content of ESP. According to him he emphasizes two characteristics; Absolute and Variable

Absolute characteristics

1. ESP is defined to meet specific needs of the learners
2. ESP makes use of underlying methodology and activities of the discipline it serves
3. ESP is centered on the language appropriate to these activities in terms of grammar, lexis, register, study skills, discourse and genre.

Variable Characteristics

1. ESP may be related to or designed for specific disciplines
2. ESP may use, in specific teaching situations, a different methodology from that of General English

3. ESP is likely to be designed for adult learners, either at a tertiary level institution or in a professional work situation. It could, however, be for learners at secondary school level

4. ESP is generally designed for intermediate or advanced students.

5. Most ESP courses assume some basic knowledge of the language systems

The definition presented by Dudley-Evans is obviously influenced by concepts of Strevens, although he has enriched it substantially by removing the absolute characteristic that ESP is "in contrast with 'General English'", and has reviewed and increased the number of variable characteristics. The division of ESP into absolute and variable characteristics, in particular, is very useful in tackling arguments about what is and is not ESP. From the definition, we can see that ESP can but is not necessarily concerned with a specific discipline, nor does it have to be aimed at a certain age group or ability range. ESP should be seen simple as an 'approach' to teaching, or what Dudley-Evans describes as an 'attitude of mind' Such a view echoes that of Hutchinson who highlights, "ESP is an approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to content and method are based on the learner's reason for learning"¹. Additionally, Hutchinson and Waters outline that "ESP is an approach to language learning and it is based on learners' need". What they mean is that ESP does not contain a certain kind of language, teaching material or methodology". They suggest that the foundation of ESP I includes the learners, the language required and the learning contexts which are based on the importance of need in ESP². From another perspective, Strevens explains a definition of ESP, which makes a distinction between four absolute characteristics and two variable characteristics. Robinson underlines the significance of needs analysis in defining ESP. Her definition is based on two key defining criteria and a number of characteristics that are important aspects for ESP. Her key criteria are that "ESP is normally goal-directed' and that ESP courses progress from a needs analysis, which aims to specify as closely as possible what accurately it is that students have to do through the medium of English". Her descriptions are that ESP courses are normally compelled by a limited time period in which their objectives have to be achieved, and are taught to adults in 'homogeneous classes' in terms of the work or specialist studies that the students are involved in. Robinson presents that ESP as an operation, which encompasses education,

¹ C.G.Ramirez, English for Specific Purposes: Brief History and Definitions,2015,Costa Rica University,p-383-384.
² M.Rahman, English for Specific Purposes: A Holistic Review,2015,Bangladesh University, p- 25-27.

preparing and practice, and drawing upon three major areas of knowledge: language, pedagogy and the students' specialist areas of interest³. When it comes to teaching English to medical students it is very crucial to address linguo-didactic approach taking into account 4 skills (listening, reading, speaking and writing) and 2 aspects (vocabulary and grammar) from pedagogical point of view. While teaching English in Medical disciplines it is remarkable to use innovative and modern technologies to catch the attention also to create learner-centered environment during the lesson. Using innovative tools plays a major role in improving the procedure of the lesson that helps students to be active during the lesson. Innovative instruments may include, audio-visual technologies such as monitor, laptop, projector, speakers, video materials and others. Regarding with authentic video materials it is important, while the role of the teacher is only conducting the lessons through video materials, meanwhile the teacher is only a passive participant as a supervisor during the lesson.

References:

1. Ramirez.C.G, English for Specific Purposes: Brief History and Definitions, Costa Rica University 2015,p-383-384.
2. M. Rahman, English for Specific Purposes: A Holistic Review, Bangladesh University, 2015, p- 25-27.
3. D. Roger and T.Swale"Genre-approach in ESP", 2017,p69
4. T.Swale, "The effectiveness of genre-based approaches in teaching professional skills", 2017.

³ D. Roger and T.Swale"Genre-approach in ESP", 2017,p69

